

Aligning Spatial Web Terms to SUMO

2024 by **David S. Douglass***

ABSTRACT

This document was created to facilitate alignment of the Spatial Web Specification (under preparation by the IEEE’s Spatial Web Working Group) with a proposed universal formal ontology, the Suggested Upper Merged Ontology (SUMO).

The Active Inference Institute has adopted SUMO as the ontological framework for formalizing its educational and analytical work on Active Inference; Active Inference is a key principle of prediction and control used by the Spatial Web.

Only the second draft of the Spatial Web Standard, IEEE P2874 Spatial Web D2 (“D2” for short), is discussed here. In any future work, this document must be updated to give precedence to the third Spatial Web draft, D3.

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OUTLINE OF CONTENTS

1. Discussion of questions that have arisen during discussion of aligning (and eventually mapping) Spatial Web topics to SUMO topics.
2. Table of formal relations in the Spatial Web specification D2, and the entities that these relations interconnect. “Entity” and “relation” are used in the sense familiar from Entity-Relation Diagrams, ERDs.
3. Table that shows, for many key terms used in the Spatial Web specification D2, areas of SUMO that are likely to contain corresponding topics, or which are portions of SUMO where topics should be created to more nearly match Spatial Web topics.

1. DISCUSSION POINTS

(1) Mereotopology/mereology

The following is the github page that holds most of the part/whole classes and rules; these are stated in the SUO-KIF language (based on KIF Knowledge Interchange Format):

<https://github.com/ontologyportal/sumo/blob/master/Merge.kif>

Examples of part-whole and spatiotemporal Classes and Relations are at:

<https://sigma.ontologyportal.org:8443/sigma/Browse.jsp?lang=EnglishLanguage&flang=SUO-KIF&kb=SUMO&term=part>

Related articles are at term=Indoors, Region, GeographicArea, SpaceRegion, TimeInterval, ImmediateFutureFn, pathInSystem, administrativeCenter, resource, Transfer, Deciding

(2) **Subject Index to SUMO (sub)ontologies**

I've attached OpenDocument text file "SUMO KIF files with sample contents.odt" (shadowed in Microsoft Word format) - a list of most of the published KIF files, with an indication of some of the topics contained in these files.

(As pointed out under (1) above, you'll find "mereotopology" listed under Merge.kif).

This roadmap is not at all exhaustive; but it does act to some degree like a topical index (unlike the search boxes on the ontologyportal.org splash page, which are strictly pointers *into* the *contents* of SUMO and WordNet).

(3) **Context and Background**

The Active Inference Institute investigated several formal ontologies when carrying out its own focused ontological work, and in 2021 selected SUMO (Suggested Upper Merged Ontology, developed by Adam Pease) as best combining breadth, rigor, and openness to collaboration.

SUMO incorporated all of Barry Smith's BFO mereology work as of the 1990s. (The latter is summarized in Smith, B. (1994) "Fiat Objects," N. Guarino, L. Vieu and S. Pribbenow (eds.), *Parts and Wholes: Conceptual Part-Whole Relations and Formal Mereology*, 11th European Conference on Artificial Intelligence, Amsterdam, 8 August 1994, 15–23.)

A 2001 overview of SUMO is presented at
<https://www.adampease.org/FOIS.pdf>

Note that rich, well-tested inference rules are provided for many entities, and can readily be supplemented in SUMO's SUO-KIF language to allow reasoning about a wide range of situations, both general (e.g. abstract algebra) and concrete (e.g. automobiles).

Here's one of Adam Pease's playlists, discussing "how to do SUMO:"
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SkruXPmN0kk&list=PLpBQIgki3izcrbaiuOH_OWWguY_duSumA&ab_channel=OntologyTalkwithAdamPease

(4) **Notes on terminology in SUMO**

SUMO-proper is the topmost part of the ontological framework, containing about 1,000 classes, and the relations that connect these classes. This part of the ontology is contained in a file called "Merged."

a. A less-general, but still not discipline-specific, network of entities is called MILO, "Mid-Level-Ontology."

b. The formal names of classes are capitalized; those of relations start with lower-case letters. (An apparent exception is the names of functions; these are capitalized, end in "Fn," and act syntactically like relations.)

Nonetheless, the systems of relations and of classes are fully integrated in the ontology (e.g. the relation relatedEvent is an instance of the class SymmetricRelation.)

(5) **Aligning and mapping between Spatial Web and SUMO**

Spatial Web proposals have mentioned the idea of aligning with, or mapping to, general-purpose formal ontologies - BFO, SUMO...

(5a) I suggest applying the procedural terms “alignment” and “mapping” advisedly.

It’s useful and unobjectionable to talk about aligning categories in the topmost, non-normative levels of presentation of Spatial Web work (notably the five-or-more Core Elements) with sub-ontologies or domains of discourse defined in *formal* ontologies.

Distinct from (‘though deeply related to) such non-technical discussion of categories of Spatial Web concepts, maximum value of the Spatial Web and VERSES initiatives will emerge with full merger of the low-level, computer-tractable concepts implicit in the Spatial Web with a formal-ontology framework. Such a merger would enable detection of logical inconsistencies at ontology-build time, and alerting on violation of the operational bounds of the defined ontology at execution time.

Adam Pease has offered the following:

“I’d suggest grounding the use of these terms in formal inference (for example, with Vampire) so there’s some objective measure of whether the spatial terms mean what people want them to mean. The file <https://github.com/ontologyportal/sumo/blob/master/tests/SpatialQs.txt> is an example of this.”

(5b) As a way to kick-start this effort, I attached an OpenDocument spreadsheet "HSML Terms - Suggested SUMO Mappings_2023-11-19.ods" (“Mappings”) (along with a version of the same contents in MS Word format).

I have listed (SUMO) Classes and Relations here simply to offer “parts lists” from which formal SUMO definitions should be either identified or constructed.

The design principles of SUMO includes formal *inference* over propositions; the ontological framework is not restricted to merely naming words and phrases. (This contrasts with the perfectly-legitimate purposes of thesauri and taxonomies, i.e. to list phrases and to indicate a few of their major interrelations.)

Several concepts found in Spatial Web documents already exist in SUMO. In the “Mappings” spreadsheet I mark a few of these with the notation “exact” in the “Fit” column.

SUMO may use a different ‘spelling’ for its representation of a given concept, e.g. “country” vs “Nation.” Even in less obvious cases, such mismatches would not obstruct equation of the Spatial Web concept with the SUMO class.

SUMO’s termFormat relation specifies how to present a term in a natural language format. In EnglishLanguage, "adrenaline" and "epinephrine" present the SUMO class Adrenaline, and "calf muscle" and "gastrocnemius" present CalfMuscle.

(6) **Hyperspatializing SUMO and Active Inference**

It’s attractive to consider eventually developing representations of SUMO and Active Inference concepts within the hyperspace framework, regardless of how interesting such definitions may prove to the Spatial Web standard.

Experts in Category Theory who have presented Active Inference webcasts are likely resources for such a blue-sky initiatives.

2. SPATIAL WEB RELATIONS

Relations	“From” element	“To” element	SUMO classes	SUMO relations
associated_with	Space	Domain		
categorized_by	Entity	Channel		
child_of	Domain	Domain		subclass
child_of	Space	Space		
connect_thru	Domain	Credential	Communication; Attaching; Planning	instrument; connected; capability
is_followed_by	Activity	Activity	TimeInterval; TimePoint	agreementExpirationDate; earlier
is_preceded_by	Activity	Activity		finishes; earlier
is_related_to	Activity	Domain	Entity	relatedInternalConcept
is_related_to	Channel	Activity	Entity	relatedInternalConcept
is_related_to	Channel	Channel	Entity	relatedInternalConcept
is_related_to	Channel	Credential	Entity	relatedInternalConcept
is_related_to	Channel	Domain	Entity	relatedInternalConcept
is_related_to	Channel	Space	Entity	relatedInternalConcept
is_spatially	Domain	Space		
is_subtask_of	Activity	Activity	IntentionalProcess	subProcess
occupies	Domain	Space	Domain	interiorPart
occurs_in	Activity	Space		
owned_via	Domain	Credential	Domain	
performed_by	Activity	Domain	IntentionalProcess	
performed_on	Activity	Activity		
performed_on	Activity	Channel		
performed_on	Activity	Credential		
performed_on	Activity	Domain		
performed_on	Activity	Space		
property_of	Credential	Domain		
resolved_by	Domain	Activity		
resolved_by	Activity	Domain		
resolved_using	Activity	Credential		distrusts
results_in	Activity	Credential		

3. SELECTED SPATIAL WEB ENTITIES ALIGNED WITH SUMO CLASSES AND RELATIONS

Elements	Sub Theory	Spatial Web Notes	*.KIF Files	SUMO Classes	SUMO Relations	Spatial Web Definition	SUMO Notes	SUMO formal definitions
Abstract space			Merge.kif	Abstract, ProcessTask,	abstractCounte rpart, abstractPart, task		Abstract: "Properties or qualities as distinguished from any particular embodiment of the properties/ qualities in a physical medium. Instances of Abstract can be said to exist in the same sense as mathematical objects such as sets and relations, but they cannot exist at a particular place and time without some physical encoding or embodiment."	Abstract is a subclass of Entity. Abstract's disjointDecompositio n consists of Quantity, Attribute, Relation, Proposition, List
action			Merge.kif	Ambulating, AutonomicPro cess, IntentionalProc ess				
Active Inference		Active Inference is a Process Theory related to Free Energy Principle .	Merge.kif, ActiveInferen ce.kif, MilitaryProce sses.kif	Judging			The subclass of Selecting where the agent opts for one belief out of a set of multiple possibilities that are available to him/ her."	Judging is a subclass of selecting. IntelligenceActivities is a subclass of Judging.
activity	ACTIVI TY	<HSML> NOTE— Activities are the basis of all entity to entity execution.	Merge.kif, Capabilities.k if, modals.kif	IntentionalProc ess	hasOccupation, industryServic eType, organizationSe rviceType	An HSML entity that represents a strictly defined series of actions to be performed by a Spatial Web Domain.	Activity: "any specific behavior;"	
aerodrome			Transportatio n.kif	Airport			Aerodrome: "an airfield equipped with control tower and hangars as well as accommodations for	

							passengers and cargo.” Airport is a subclass of AirTransitway, LandTransitway, and TransitTerminal.	
agent			Merge.kif, Government. kif, Justice.kif, Law.kif	CaseRole	agent	A person or thing that takes an active role or produces a specified effect.	A SUMO relation agent links a Process to an AutonomousAgent. “Agent” is a core topic in the Active Inference Ontology: “Entity as modeled by Active Inference , with Internal State separated from External State by Blanket State.”	Agent is a subclass of Object. (relation) agent is a subrelation of involved in event . Agent is an instance of case role.
airplane			Mid-level- ontology.kif, Transportatio n.kif	Airplane, Aircraft	absoluteHeight		Airplane: “aircraft that has a fixed wing and is powered by propellers or jets.”	
asset			Merge.kif, Mid-level- ontology.kif	AutonomousA gent, Giving, PropertyFn, Sharing	possesses			
assign			Merge.kif		AssignmentFn		If F is a Function with a value for the objects denoted by N1,..., NK, then (AssignmentFn F N1 ... NK) is the value of applying F to the objects denoted by N1,..., NK. Otherwise, the value is undefined.	AssignmentFn maps a Function to an Entity.
augmented reality			SpatialWeb.k if, Mid-level- ontology.kif, RecreationOr Exercise.kif	MediaSystem, VideoGamePla yer		Type of mixed reality system in which virtual world data are embedded and/or registered with the representation of physical world	“Augmented reality” is a supplemental topic in the Active Inference Ontology.	

						data. (ISO/IEC 18039 2019 [B44], 3.1.2)		
authority	AUTHORITY		Merge.kif, Government.kif, mondial.kif	NormativeAttribute, PoliticalOrganization, SocialRole		Namespace that identifies a hierarchy of hyperspace objects. Syn hyperspace authority.	Authority: "official permission or approval;" "an administrative unit of government;" "persons who exercise (administrative) control over others;"	
authority naming			SpatialWeb.kif		associateWithStatus	An activity hyperspace authority address system for humans and machines.		
autonomous agent			Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif, Biography.kif, Capabilities.kif, Catalog.kif, Economy.kif, Emotion.kif, engineering.kif, FinancialOntology.kif, Government.kif, Justice.kif, Law.kif, Media.kif, modals.kif, Transportation.kif	AutonomousAgent	activityCapability, agent, agentName, agentOperatesInArea, areaOfResponsibility, associateWithStatus	Entity that carries out a set of operations on behalf of a user or another program with some degree of independence or autonomy, and in so doing, employ some knowledge or representation of the user's goals or desires.	Autonomous Agent: "Something or someone that can act on its own and produce changes in the world."	

Biology			Mid-level-ontology.kif, Biography.	Biology, Biologist	hasExpertise			Biology is a subclass of Science. hasExpertise is a relation between a Human and a FieldOfStudy.
book			Mid-level-ontology.kif, Media.kif	Book			A Book is a HardcoverDocument.	
city			Merge.kif	City, Government, LandArea			City: "A LandArea of relatively small size, inhabited by a community of people, and having some sort of political structure."	
claim	CLAIM		Merge.kif	NormativeAttribute, LegalAction, Ordering, Requesting, Permission			Claim: "an established or recognized right;" "an assertion of a right (as to money or property);" "demand for something as rightful or due;" a demand especially in the phrase 'the call of duty;'" "an informal right to something;" "	
cloud computing			SpatialWeb.kif, Internet.kif, ComputingBrands.kif	CommunicationSystem; Internet		Paradigm for enabling network access to a scalable and elastic pool of shareable physical or virtual resources with self-service provisioning and administration on-demand. (ISO/IEC 17788 2014 [B43], 3.2.5)		

collection			Merge.kif	Collection			Collections have members like Classes, but, unlike Classes, they have a position in space-time and members can be added and subtracted without thereby changing the identity of the Collection. Some examples are toolkits, repeated actions, football teams, and flocks of sheep.	Collection is a subclass of Object
Color	domain		Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif	ColorAttribute	color			
company			Merge.kif	Corporation, Business	customerValue		Company: “an institution created to conduct business”	
concern			Merge.kif	Proposition		A matter of relevance or importance to a stakeholder. (ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010 2022 [B59], 3.10)	Concern: ‘Something that interests you because it is important or affects you; "the safety of the ship is the captain's concern.”’	
connect			Merge.kif		connected	`	(connected A B) means that A meetsSpatially B or that A overlapsSpatially B.	connected is a relation between an Object and an Object.
connection					connected			
container			Mid-level-ontology.kif	Container			Container: “any object that can be used to hold things.”	
Content	domain		Merge.kif	Object, SelfConnected Object	contains			contains holds between a SelfConnectedObject and an Object
contents			Merge.kif	Collection	located, member			

context			Merge.kif	Text	authors, publishes	A temporally fixed boundary which defines the aspects, contents and connections of a domain.a temporally fixed boundary which defines the aspects, contents and connections of a domain.		Text is a subclass of Artifact, ContentBearingObject, and LinguisticExpression.
contract		NOTE—The original term has been changed to lowercase.	Mid-level-ontology.kif, Media.kif, UXExperimentalTerms.kif	Contract, ContractDocument, Law		A binding agreement between two parties, especially enforceable by law, or a similar internal agreement wholly within an organization [ISO/IEC/IEEE 12207 2008]. A contract is an agreement between two or more parties regarding a course of action. The formality of a contract can range from a simple informal oral description to a formal written instrument. (IEEE 730-2014 [B30])	Contract: “A binding agreement between two or more persons that is enforceable by law.” Contract is a subattribute of ActiveAgreement. Naked promise is the opposite of contract and of Promise. Treaty is a subattribute of contract. Please NOTE WELL: If (as here) an existing SUMO term with “Contract” and “contract”’s almost the meaning required for an HSML/HSTP concept, it may be possible to add logical rules that add nuance to the existing term, but also confine application of the SUMO class to the specific Spatial Web situation desired. If a HSML concept shares almost all the behavior of an existing SUMO class, but is incompatible with it in one particular, it is often	

							possible to define the new term to inherit from the same parent(s) as the existing term, and tweak the resulting definition to act as needed.	
country			Media.kif, Music.kif	Nation, CountryID, Group	NationalAnthe mFn, StreetAddressF n, citizen, inflationRateIn Country		Country: “the territory occupied by a nation;” “ a politically organized body of people under a single government;” “the people who live in a nation or country.”	CountryID is a subclass of TerritoryID.
county			Media.kif	County, GeographicArea			County: “(United States) the largest administrative district within a state.”	County is a subclass of GeopoliticalArea. County is a subclass of LandArea.
create CREDENTIAL			Merge.kif	ContentDevelopment, ContentBearingObject				ContentDevelopment is a subclass of IntentionalProcess
Creator	domain		Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif	AutonomousAgent	creator		(creator ?AGENT ?ENTITY) means that some AutonomousAgent ?AGENT is the creator of some Entity ?ENTITY"	creator is a relation between an AutonomousAgent and an Entity
credential	CREDE NTIAL	<HSML> NOTE— Modified from IEEE 802.1AR®- 2018 [B31]	Merge.kif	ContentBearingObject, FactualText		Information that an entity (a person or device) possesses that allow it to make a verifiable claim of identity, i.e., to be authenticated.	Credential: “a document attesting to the truth of certain stated facts.” Identification: “evidence of identity; something that identifies a person or thing.”	

decentralized identifier			SpatialWeb.kif, Merge.kif, QoSontology.kif	Decentralized ResourceIdentifier		Identifier in the format of the W3C Decentralized Identifier. Syn DID. (W3C did-core)	DecentralizedResourceIdentifier should be defined in the (new) SpatialWebModeling.kif, as a subclass of UniformResourceIdentifier (parallel to UniformResourceLocator and UniformResourceName); and possibly also a subclass of InternetAddress and/or of StandardIdentifier. UniformResourceIdentifier is a subclass of ContentBearingObject.	
decentralized identifier definition			Mid-level-ontology.kif	Identifier	browserID, userIDString			
			Merge.kif	Communication, ContentBearingObject, Proposition	containsInformation, realization, represents			
DGGS		Discrete Global Grid System, ISO 19170-1:2021. See also https://docs.ogc.org/as/20-040r3/20-040r3.html ; https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Discrete_global_grid	Merge.kif	GraphArc, GraphNode	arcWeight, graphPart, subGraph, systemPart			
DID		decentralized identifier	SpatialWeb.kif	Identifier	browserID, userIDString	See decentralized identifier.		
dimension			Merge.kif, Cars.kif, ComputerInput.kif,	GraphPath, PhysicalDimension, LengthMeasure	physicalDomain, altitude, approximateDiameter, cylinderBore,	The number of degrees of freedom of a physical quantity. An electric field,	Dimension: “one of three Cartesian coordinates that determine a position in space;” “the magnitude of something in a particular	PhysicalDimension is a subclass of Quantity

			engineering.kif		defaultMaximumSphereRadius, geometricDistance	which is a spatial vector quantity, has dimension 3. (ISO/IEC/IEEE 21451-1 2010 [B57], 3.44)	direction (especially length or width or height).“	
discovery			Merge.kif	Learning, Discovering			Learning: “The Class of Processes which relate to the acquisition of information.” Discovering: “Finding something that was sought; restricted to cases discovering something Physical.”	Learning is a subclass of IntentionalPsychologicalProcess
distributed computing			SpatialWeb.kif	Device	effectiveRange, equipmentCount	Model of computing in which a set of nodes coordinates its activities by means of digital messages passed between the nodes. (ISO/IEC TR 23188 2020 [B56], 3.1.1)		
distributed ledger			Merge.kif	Calculating	agent	A ledger that is shared across a set of DLT nodes and synchronized between the DLT nodes using a consensus mechanism. (ISO 22739 2020 [B38], 3.22)	Ledger: “a record in which commercial accounts are recorded.” Counting and Measuring are subclasses of Calculating.	
distributed universal domain graph system			SpatialWeb.kif, Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif	Device	effectiveRange, equipmentCount	The set of coordinated Spatial Web Nodes that provide services on the distributed	Device: “an instrumentality invented for a particular purpose.”	

						UDG. Syn distributed UDG system.		
domain	DOMAIN	<HSML>	SpatialWeb.kif, Merge.kif	Entity, Object, Physical, Process		Sphere of knowledge, influence, or activity. The subject area to which the user applies a program is the domain of the software. See also entity; Spatial Web Domain.	("domain" is the name of a specific, widely-used relation in SUMO.) It may prove appropriate to translate the technical HSML term "domain" by one of the SUMO classes "Object," "Physical," or "Process." If no exiting SUMO class is a good gloss for "domain," it may not be necessary to represent this term by any single, specific SUMO class, either new or existing. SUMO class.	
drone			Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif	Aircraft, Device, Vehicle			Aircraft: "a vehicle that can fly." Vehicle: "a conveyance that transports people or objects."	
Earth Science			Mid-level-ontology.kif	Science				
Emotion	domain		emotion.kif	EmotionalState, StateOfMind				
employee			Merge.kif, FinancialOntology.kif	Employee, Human, Employment, FinancialContract, ServiceContract			Employee: "a worker who is hired to perform a job." Employment: "the occupation for which you are paid."	

entity	ENTIT Y	NOTE—An entity exists whether data about it are available or not.	Merge.kif	Entity, Physical, Abstract	relatedExternal Concept	Concrete or abstract thing that exists, did exist, or might exist, including associations among these things. (ISO/IEC 15944-5 2008 [B42], 3.47)	Entity: “that which is perceived or known or inferred to have its own distinct existence (living or nonliving).” relatedExternalConcept: "Used to signify a three-place relation between a concept in an external knowledge source, a concept in the SUMO, and the name of the other knowledge source." ===== Entity, the SUMO universal class, is exhaustively partitioned into physical and abstract .Entities can be ordered, counted, named... Entities can confer norms, rights, obligations, referred to things... Entities can create, be acted on as patients... Physical is exhaustively partitioned into (Further note: SUMO class of Object and Process. Class Abstract is disjointly decomposed; into Quantity, Attribute, Relation, Proposition, and List.)	
Euclidean space		NOTE 1—The usual geometrical three-dimensional space is a Euclidean point space. Four-dimensional vectors used in special relativity	Merge.kif	AreaMeasure, PhysicalQuantity, Quantity, Set		Real vector space or real point space for which a scalar product is defined for any two vectors. ([B94] [B94], Clause 02-03-19, modified –	Euclidean space: “a space in which Euclid's axioms and definitions apply; a metric space that is linear and finite-dimensional.”	

		are elements of a non-Euclidean point space because the scalar product of a vector by itself may be negative. Another example of non-Euclidean vector space is the set of n-bit words formed of the digits zero and one with addition modulo two, because the scalar product of a vector by itself can be zero for a non-zero vector. NOTE 2—Euclidean space is a type of vector space.				Note 2 has been added.)		
fan			Merge.kif, Media.kif, RecreationOrExercise.kif, UXExperimentalTerms.kif	SocialRole, WebSite	confirmedRegisteredUser, accountAtSite		Fan: “an ardent follower and admirer;” “an enthusiastic devotee of sports (etc.).” SocialRole is a subclass of RelationalAttribute Only a Human can be a fan.	
game	activity		Merge.kif	Game			Game: “a contest with rules to determine a winner.”	Game is a subclass of Contest and of RecreationOrExercise
Gender	domain		Merge.kif	NonBinaryGender, SexAttribute				
graph space		NOTE—Graph space is a type of hyperspace.	Merge.kif	Graph	abstractCountertpart, graphMeasure, graphPart, subGraph, CutSetFn,	A set of nodes and edges such that every edge has both a source node and a target node.	Graph: “to represent by means of a graph.” Graph is a subclass of Proposition. Subclasses of Graph include DirectedGraph,	

					MinimalCutSet Fn		MultiGraph, PseudoGraph.	
hangar	space		Merge.kif	Building	numberOfFloors		Hangar: “a large structure at an airport where aircraft can be stored and maintained.”	
hierarchy			Merge.kif	List, Organization		An arrangement where the elements of the organization are represented as being “above”, “below”, or “at the same level as” one another.	Hierarchy: “the organization of people at different ranks in an administrative body;” “a series of ordered groupings of people or things within a system.”	
holon		NOTE—Holons can be understood as the constituent part– wholes of a hierarchy.	SpatialWeb.kif, Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif, Cars.kif, engineering.kif, Food.kif, Medicine.kif, Music.kif, WMD.kif	Collection, Organism, SelfConnectedObject, SpatialRelation, subProcess	contains, part, ancestor, inhabits, mother, parasite, sheddingBodyPart, AgentOfOrganismFn, chromosomeSetCount, controlGroup,	Something that is simultaneously a whole in and of itself, as well as being part of a larger whole. (Edwards [B15])	Organism: “a living thing that has (or can develop) the ability to act or function independently;” “a system considered analogous in structure or function to a living body; ‘the social organism’ (Collection).” A SelfConnectedObject is any Object that does not consist of two or more disconnected parts. A (Physical) Object can be part of a (Physical) Object. contains and part are disjoint relations, distinguished by whether the parts can be separated. (SUMO includes some 60 logical rules of inference defining the conditions for and the consequences of	

							one Physical Object containing another.)	
HSML			SpatialWeb.kif, Merge.kif	NormativeAttribute		See Hyperspace Modelling Language.	NormativeAttribute: "A Class containing all of the Attributes that are specific to morality, legality, aesthetics, etiquette, etc. Many of these attributes express a judgement that something ought or ought not to be the case."	
HSTP			SpatialWeb.kif, Merge.kif	NormativeAttribute		See Hyperspace Transaction Protocol.		
Hyperspace Modelling Language			SpatialWeb.kif, Merge.kif	HyperspaceModelingLanguage, Formula, NormativeAttribute, Proposition		A human- and machine-readable modeling language and semantic data ontology schema that describes objects, relations, actions, activities and their permissions. Syn HSML. HSML.	(Elaborate, precise definitions for HSML and HTML statements can be written in SUMO's logic-based language if desired.)	
Hyperspace Transaction Protocol			SpatialWeb.kif, Merge.kif	HyperspaceTransactionProtocol, Formula, NormativeAttribute		Generic protocol designed to underwrite the automated contracting that is		

				bute, Proposition		required to build a coherent, decentralized, secure, and privacy-respecting Spatial Web. Syn HSTP. See also Spatial Web.		
interoperability			SpatialWeb.kif, Merge.kif		capability	Ability of two or more systems or applications to exchange information and to mutually use the information that has been exchanged. (ISO/IEC 17788 2014 [B43], 3.1.5)	Capability: “the quality of being capable, physically or intellectually or legally.” Compatibility: “capability of existing or performing in harmonious or congenial combination.”	
ledger			Mid-level-ontology.kif	FinancialText		Information store that keeps records of transactions that are intended to be final, definitive and immutable. (ISO 22739 2020 [B38], 3.43)	Ledger: “a record in which commercial accounts are recorded.” FinancialBill is a subclass of FinancialText	
lobby			Merge.kif	Room			Lobby: “a large entrance or reception room or area.”	
Location	domain		Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif, MilitaryProcesses.kif, Weather.kif	Locating, MeasuringList	located, locatedAtTime		Locating: "Discover the location of, determine the place of, find by searching or examining." (locatedAtTime ?OBJ ?TIME ?PLACE) means that during the time specified by ?TIME, ?OBJ was in the location specified by ?PLACE. MeasuringList: “a	located is a relation between a Physical and an Object. locatedAtTime is a relation among an Object, a TimePosition, and an Object.

							sequence of Measuring Processes arranged in a List.”	
manifest	domain		Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif	Certificate	issuedBy		Manifest: “a customs document listing the contents put on a ship or plane.” A Certificate is a subclass of Text. A Certificate is issuedBy a CognitiveAgent.	
mechanic			Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif	OccupationalTrade, Position			Mechanic: “someone whose occupation is repairing and maintaining automobiles (etc.);” “a craftsman skilled in operating machine tools.” OccupationalTrade is a subclass of SkilledOccupation and of ManualLabor.	
medical supplies			Merge.kif, Medicine.kif	Quantity	concentration		Supplies: “an amount of something available for use.”	
metagraph			SpatialWeb.kif, Merge.kif	Graph	abstractCountertpart, graphMeasure, graphPart, subGraph, CutSetFn, MinimalCutSetFn	Holonic hypergraph whose nodes and edges can define additional relationships.	Graph is a subclass of Proposition	

mixed reality system			SpatialWeb.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif, RecreationOrExercise.kif	MediaSystem, VideoGamePlayer		System that uses a mixture of representations of physical world data and virtual world data as its presentation medium. (ISO/IEC 18039 2019 [B44], 3.1.13)		
model			Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif, ComputingBrands.kif, engineering.kif, Catalog.kif, FinancialOntology.kif	Model, EngineeringComponent, IntentionalProcess, Abstract, AutonomousAgent, Proposition, Icon, Blueprint, Map, Planning, Making	models, FailureFn, abstractCounterpart, abstractPart, achievement, benchmark, offers, brandIcon		Model: “the act of representing something (usually on a smaller scale);” “a representative form or pattern;” A Model models an EngineeringComponent;” “a hypothetical description of a complex entity or process;” “representation of something (sometimes on a smaller scale);” “create a representation or model of;” “construct a model of;” “model an airplane.””	The Active Inference Ontology defines several kinds of model. “Recognition Model is the kind of Model that affords Variational Inference, which lets us calculate or approximate a probability distribution. Recognition Model is a synonym for Variational Model.” ”A Recognition Model updates Internal State parameters that correspond to External State (including Hidden State causes of environment states), Blanket State, and Internal State (meta-modeling). In contrast, Generative Model take those same Internal State parameter Estimators

								and emits expected or plausible observations.“ “Generative Model is a formalism that describes the mapping between Hidden State, and Expectations of Action Prediction , Sensory outcome.” “In Dayan and Abbot (2001)’s treatment of Recognition Models, the probability of a Hidden State (causes) given Sensory Data (effects) under some parameter.” “A Hierarchical Model represents a hierarchy of Estimators, which operate at different spatiotemporal timescales (so they track features at different scales); all carrying out Predictive Processing.” “Agent has Agency.”
Mona Lisa	entity		Merge.kif	Object				Object is a subclass of Physical
monitoring			Merge.kif	Listening, Looking				
norm			Merge.kif	NormativeAttribute		A standard, or principle of right action, binding upon the members of a group and serving to guide,	Norm: “a standard or model or pattern regarded as typical.” A NormativeAttribute is a subclass of RelationalAttribute	

						control, or regulate proper and acceptable behavior.		
nurse			Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif, Medicine.kif	MedicalDoctor, Position, Profession, Human			MedicalDoctor is an instance of Profession. Position is a subclass of SocialRole. Profession is disjoint from OccupationalTrade.	
online home	domain		Merge.kif, Media.kif, UXExperimentalTerms.kif	WebSite, GroupOfPeople, Region	categoryOf, confirmedRegisteredUser			
order	activity		Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif	Directing, PurchaseOrder, Requesting			Order: "a request for something to be made, supplied, or served." PurchaseOrder: "a commercial document used to request someone to supply something in return for payment and providing specifications and quantities." PurchaseOrder is a subclass of FinancialText. Requesting Directing is a subclass of	
Owner	domain		Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif, FinancialOntology.kif	AcademicDegree, FamilyBusiness, FinancialAccount	possesses		possesses: "Relation that holds between an AutonomousAgent and an Object when the AutonomousAgent has ownership of the Object. Note that this is distinct from having the right to use or be located at a particular object, for example, by Renting."	

park			Mid-level-ontology.kif	Park			Park: “a large area of land preserved in its natural state as public property.” Park is a subclass of LandArea	
part			Merge.kif		contains		Contains: "The relation of spatial containment for two separable objects. When the two objects are not separable (e.g. an automobile and one of its seats), the relation of part should be used. (contains ?OBJ1 ?OBJ2) means that the SelfConnectedObject ?OBJ1 has a space (i.e. a HoleRegion) which is at least partially filled by ?OBJ2."	contains is a relation between a SelfConnectedObject and an Object.
peer-to-peer			Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif	Device	powerComponent, equipmentCount	Relating to, using, or being a network of equal peers that share information and resources with each other directly without relying on a central entity. (ISO 27729 2012 [B39], 3.56)	Device is a subclass of Artifact	
pick	activity		Merge.kif	Pursuing, Selecting			Pick: “the act of choosing or selecting;” “look for and gather.” Pursuing is a subclass of IntentionalProcess. Selecting is a subclass of IntentionalPsychologicalProcess.	

pick-and-pack	activity		Merge.kif	Pursuing, Putting, Selecting			Pick: “the act of choosing or selecting;” “look for and gather.” Pack: “arrange in a container.” Pursuing is a subclass of IntentionalProcess. Selecting is a subclass of IntentionalPsychologicalProcess. Putting Transfer.is a subclass of	
query			Merge.kif	Directing, Questioning, Requesting			Query: “an instance of questioning;” “to pose a question.” Questioning is a subclass of Directing	
real-time			SpatialWeb.kif, QoSontology.kif	ComputerTask		Pertaining to a system or mode of operation in which computation is performed during the actual time that an external process occurs, in order that the computation results can be used to control, monitor, or respond in a timely manner to the external process. (ISO/IEC/IEEE 24765 2017 [B58], 3.3327)	ComputerTask is a subclass of ComputerProcess	
receiving site	space		Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif, Hotel.kif	Region, Transportation	capableAtLocation, providesDestination		Site: “Physical position in relation to the surroundings;” “assign a location to.”	A TransportationCompany provides a Destination to a Region.
register			SpatialWeb.kif, Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif	Book, Certificate	issuedBy	Set of files containing identifiers assigned to items with	Register: “a book in which names and transactions are listed.” A Certificate is a subclass of Text. A	

						descriptions of the associated items (ISO 19135-1 2015 [B37], 4.1.9)	Certificate is issuedBy a CognitiveAgent.	
reinforcement learning			Merge.kif, UXExperimentalTerms.kif	Learning, Guiding, Process, Experimenting	enjoys, agent, causes, benefits, experiencer, hinders, experimentalControlProcess	An action taken by an agent in an environment to maximize the notion of cumulative reward.	Reinforcement: “an act performed to strengthen approved behavior;” “(psychology) a stimulus that strengthens or weakens the behavior that produced it.” Learning: “the cognitive process of acquiring skill or knowledge.” Learning is a subclass of IntentionalPsychologicalProcess. A CognitiveAgent enjoys an IntentionalProcess.	
repair	activity		Merge.kif	Repairing, Maintaining			Repairing: “the act of putting something in working order again.”	Repairing is a subclass of IntentionalProcess, and is internally related to maintaining.
representation		NOTE— Representations can be passive or active. A passive representation reflects the state of a particular slice of the world, in something approaching real time. An active representation, on the other hand, changes the state of that system based	Merge.kif	IntentionalProcess, Stating, Imagining, Text		Creation of a model that can be used to describe some aspect of a world.	Representation: “an activity that stands as an equivalent of something or results in an equivalent” or “the act of representing; standing in for someone or some group and speaking with authority in their behalf;” “a presentation to the mind in the form of an idea or image;” “a statement of facts and reasons made in appealing or protesting;” “a factual statement made by one	“Representation” is a core topic in the Active Inference Ontology: “A structural correspondence between some Random variable inside a System and some Random variable outside the System (isomorphism being the strongest kind of correspondence), such that the System

		upon some user action.					party in order to induce another party to enter into a contract.”	engages in Inference carried out by the System maintains the correspondence.”
robot			Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif, ComputingBrands.kif	Device, maxDeviceOperatingTemp	effectiveRange, EquipmentType		Robot: “a mechanism that can move automatically”	
route			Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif, routeInSystem, Transportation.kif	Roadway, Transitway	distanceOnPath, routeBetween, transitwayCapacityCount, transitwayCapacityRate, StreetAddressFunction, postStreet	“An actor request[s] the calculation of a route based on start and end points, and possibly waypoints. The route is created for a DOMAIN that may be associated with several SPACES. The Processing service creates the route as a new DOMAIN and provides the route DOMAIN to the client.”	Route: “an open way (generally public) for travel or transportation;” “an established line of travel or access.” ===== Transitway is a subclass of Region. Transitway is a subclass of SelfConnectedObject.	
sequence diagram				Text			WordNet: “flowchart” (a diagram of the sequence of operations in a computer program or an accounting system)	Text is a subclass of Artifact, ContentBearingObject, LinguisticExpression
Shape	domain		Merge.kif	ShapeAttribute, ShapeChange	shape			

shipment	activity		Merge.kif, Mid-level- ontology.kif	Artifact, Transfer	equipmentType		Shipment: “the act of sending off something” or “goods carried by a large vehicle.”	
Size	domain		Mid-level- ontology.kif	SizeAttribute				
space	SPACE	<HSML>	Merge.kif, Mid-level- ontology.kif, Transportatio n.kif	AreaMeasure, DirectionalAttr ibute, PhysicalQuanti ty, Quantity, Region, SpaceRegion	EventLocated, InnerBoundary Fn, VelocityFn	A set whose elements are related by a notion of path, such that paths compose associatively.Syn hyperspace.	Space: “an area reserved for some particular purpose;” “the unlimited expanse in which everything is located;”	
spatial contract		NOTE 1—Spatial contracts can combine geographic and temporal bounds, with trade requirements for financial and spatial transactions (physical activities and can be graphically visualized for users). NOTE 2— A spatial contract is a binary expression over a hyperspace transaction, including the related objects’ previous and requested state, as well as the requesting and approving objects states, that returns true if the transaction is valid	SpatialWeb.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif, FinancialOntology.kif, MilitaryProcesses.kif	Contract, FinancialContr act	areaOfOperati on	An n-dimensional extension of a smart or autonomous contract in that it expresses who, how, and under what conditions an actor may interact with an object in space and can self-execute if those conditions are met.	Contract: “A binding agreement between two or more persons that is enforceable by law.”	

		relative to the previous and next states.						
spatial coordinates	space		Merge.kif, Geography.kif	Longitude, PlaneAngleMeasure, Region	headingWRTCompassNorth		Elevation: “distance of something above a reference point” or “angular distance above the horizon (especially of a celestial object).” Location: “a point or extent in space.”	
spatial query			Merge.kif, MilitaryProcesses.kif	Questioning	areaOfOperation		Questioning is a subclass of Directing	
spatial representation	space		Merge.kif	Region				
Spatial Web Client		NOTE—Spatial Web Clients can also communicate in a peer-to-peer fashion.	SpatialWeb.kif, Merge.kif, QoSontology.kif	Computer		Node that communicates with Spatial Web servers in a client-server relationship, to provide users with respective views of the graphs in various forms. See also peer-to-peer.	Client: “(computer science) any computer that is hooked up to a computer network.”	

Spatial Web Domain		NOTE 1—Domains can be geopolitical (e.g., Earth, EMEA), authority-driven (e.g., BigCo, SpatialWebFoundation) or IP work-related (e.g., ArthurianWorld). Domains make use of both DIDs and Qualified Names. NOTE 2—A given domain identifier may have multiple associated qualified names.	SpatialWeb.kif, Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif, Geography.kif, Government.kif, Justice.kif, Law.kif, Transportation.kif, UXExperimentalTerms.kif	GeopoliticalArea, Human, FieldOfStudy, WebListingCategory	BirthsPerThousandFn, CitizenryFn, ConstitutionFn, categoryID, hasExpertise, etc.	Entities in hyperspace that confer rights and identifies a set of assets, scenes, permissions and related domains.	Domain: “territory over which rule or control is exercised;” “people in general; especially a distinctive group of people with some shared interest;” “the content of a particular field of knowledge.”	
Spatial Web Domain Server		NOTE—A Spatial Web Domain Server is critical to spatial content retrieval and spatial transaction validation, whereby the rules for particular areas can be described as spatial permissions in their associated assets.	SpatialWeb.kif, Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif, QoSontology.kif, ComputingBrands.kif	Computer, Device, Server	computerRunning, connectedPeripheral, deviceAccount, hardwareType, etc.	Networked server that provides location-based identification of hyperspace assets and ownership information to Spatial Web Domains. See also Spatial Web Domain.	Server: “(computer science) a computer that provides client stations with access to files and printers as shared resources to a computer network.”	

Spatial Web Identifier		NOTE 1—A SWID includes implicit reference ability to SWID Documents via registered “methods”, which specify how to both resolve and revoke SWIDs and how to write SWID Documents themselves. NOTE 2—The SWID can be thought of as a pointer to the context of a resource, not just the resource itself, and utilizes the universal domain graph to maintain a certain degree of statefulness about the resource(s) in question.	SpatialWeb.kif, Merge.kif, QoSontology.kif, UXExperimentalTerms.kif	Identifier, Name	browserID, categoryID	Identifier of a hyperspace object formulated as a URL conforming to a DID. Syn SWID.	Identifier: “a symbol that establishes the identity of the one bearing it.”	
Spatial Web Node			SpatialWeb.kif, Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif, QoSontology.kif	Computer, Device	computerRunning, connectedPeripheral, deviceAccount, hardwareType, etc.	Computing machine connected to the internet, capable of exchanging HSTP messages.	Node: “(computer science) any computer that is hooked up to a computer network.	
stakeholder			Merge.kif, Government.kif	SocialRole, AutonomousAgent	candidateForPosition, CognitiveAgent, roleAppointsRole	A role, position, individual, organization, or classes thereof, having an interest, right, share, or claim, in an entity of interest.	Stakeholder: “someone entrusted to hold the stakes for two or more persons betting against one another; must deliver the stakes to the winner.”	

						(ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010 2022 [B59], 3.17)		
stakeholder perspective			Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif	CognitiveAgent, Proposition, SocialRole	conforms, propositionOwner	way of thinking about an entity of interest, especially as it relates to concerns (ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010 2022 [B59], 3.18, modified – The original example has been removed.)	Stakeholder: “someone entrusted to hold the stakes for two or more persons betting against one another; must deliver the stakes to the winner.” Perspective: “a way of regarding situations or topics etc.”	
state			Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif	Government, StateGovernment, StateOrProvince				
Subject	domain		Merge.kif	FieldOfStudy, Object				
supply chain	channel		Merge.kif	Putting, Selling, Quantity	Collection	BoughtItemsFn	Chain: “a series of things depending on each other as if linked together - ‘the chain of command’; ‘a complicated concatenation of circumstances.’”	
technician			Merge.kif	Human, Position	subordinatePosition		Technician: “someone whose occupation involves training in a specific technical process” or “someone known for high skill in some technique.”	
terminate action			QoSontology.kif	DeletingData	capability, patient			
terminate session			QoSontology.kif	DeletingData	capability, patient			

terminating ACTIVITY			QoSontology.kif	DeletingData	capability, patient			
Texture	domain		Merge.kif	TextureAttribute				
Time	domain		Merge.kif	TimeMeasure, TimePoint, TimePosition	temporallyBetweenOrEqual, time		TimePoint: "An extensionless point on the universal timeline."	time is a relation between a Physical and a TimePosition. temporallyBetweenOrEqual is a relation among 3 TimePoint. TimePoint is a subclass of TimePosition. Each TimePosition TimeInterval TimePoint. Is either
tourism	activity		Economy.kif	TourismIndustry			Tourism: "the business of providing services to tourists"	
transform			Merge.kif	Function	LatitudeFn, closedOn, range			
trust			SpatialWeb.kif, Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif	SocialInteraction, Proposition, Psychological Attribute	accountInformation, conforms	An assured reliance on the character, ability, strength, or truth of someone or something.	Trust: "a trustful relationship," "complete confidence in a person or plan etc," "certainty based on past experience."	
universal domain graph		NOTE—The universal domain graph is the complete Spatial Web metagraph.	SpatialWeb.kif, Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif, Geography.kif, mondial.kif, Weather.kif	Graph, Longitude, PlaneAngleMeasure, Region, ContentDevelopment	Device, CutSetFn, graphMeasure, graphPart, headingWRTC compassNorths SubGraph, MinimalCutSet Fn	A distributed metagraph which contains all relationships between all known SWIDs in the Spatial Web. Syn UDG.	Graph: "to represent by means of a graph."	

Urban Digital Twin			SpatialWeb.kif, Merge.kif	Certificate	issuedBy		Proxy: “a power of attorney document given by shareholders of a corporation authorizing a specific [action].” Alias: “a name that has been assumed temporarily.”	
vector space		NOTE—Vector space is a type of hyperspace, and Euclidean space is a type of vector space.	Merge.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif	PlaneAngleMeasure, GraphArc	CutSetFn, graphMeasure, graphPart, MinimalCutSetFn	Type of space composed of dimensions where each dimension is the set of real numbers.	Vector: “a straight line segment whose length is magnitude and whose orientation in space is direction;” “a variable quantity that can be resolved into components.”	
virtual reality			SpatialWeb.kif, Mid-level-ontology.kif, RecreationOrExercise.kif	MediaSystem, VideoGamePlayer		An artificial environment presented in the computer.	VideoGamePlayer is a subclass of MediaSystem	
warehouse	space		Mid-level-ontology.kif	Warehouse			Warehouse is a subclass of CommercialBuilding	
WeRLogistics			Mid-level-ontology.kif	TransportationCompany			Warehouse: “a storehouse for goods and merchandise.” A TransportationCompany provides a Destination to a Region.	

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“One mereology topic I find difficult is that around holons, holonic and holarchy. The concept came from biological ecosystems and has been developed in holonic manufacturing systems.

“Gabriel René uses the term regularly. My challenge is to write a specification of the concept sufficient for an IEEE standard. Have you used these terms?”

REFERENCES

Resource	Date	Name of file or video	Location	DOI
P2874™/D2 Draft Standard for Spatial Web Protocol, Architecture and Governance	2023-01	IEEE P2874 Spatial Web D2.pdf		
An Overview of the Spatial Web, Gabriel René	2023		https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lcIwsTYGt-8	
IEEE P2874 Spatial Web, Architecture and Governance Working Group	2024		https://sagroups.ieee.org/2874/	
Suggested Upper Merged Ontology (SUMO)	2024		https://ontologyportal.org/	
Aligning Spatial Web Terminology to SUMO (present document)	2024	Aligning Spatial Web Terms to SUMO.docx		https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11055372
Aligning Spatial Web Terminology to SUMO	2024	Aligning Spatial Web Terms to SUMO.pdf		
Spreadsheet from which Section 2, SPATIAL WEB RELATIONS, is excerpted	2024	Spatial Web Relations (D2) Aligned to SUMO.xlsx		
Spreadsheet from which Section 3, SELECTED SPATIAL WEB ENTITIES ALIGNED WITH SUMO CLASSES AND RELATIONS, is excerpted	2024	Spatial Web Entities (D2) Aligned to SUMO.xlsx		